

National Open Access Monitor Survey: Organisational Identity: Update Submissions

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The National Open Access Monitor Survey: Organisational Identity was originally run during October 2023, and reopened in January 2024 for updates.

This form is for organisations/entities that have submitted a response to that survey, and would like to update their answer.

- It is intended that the original respondent will update their entry. If you are not the original respondent, please contact catherine.ferris@mu.ie first to verify that you have permission to update the entry.
- In order to update the entry, you will need to refer to the original submission, and indicate which answer is to be overwritten. The original submission is viewable here: [\[download link\]](#)
- This form is intended to capture one update to one answer in the original submission. If you would like to overwrite more than one answer, this form can be submitted multiple times, one for each answer to be overwritten.
- Updates will be incorporated into the Master Survey Change File here: <https://zenodo.org/records/10100896>

If your organisation has not submitted to the survey, **do not complete this form**. If you would like to submit for the first time, please complete the form here: [\[link\]](#). A submission from an organisation that has not already submitted will not be actioned.

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Introduction

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Introduction

The National Open Access Monitor Survey: Organisational Identity is carried out under the National Open Access Monitoring project, funded by Ireland's National Open Research Forum (NORF) under the NORF Open Research Fund 2022 to address one of the six priority actions of Ireland's [National Action Plan for Open Research 2022-2023](#).

The purpose of this survey is to empower stakeholders to self-identify how their entities will be represented in the National Open Access Monitor. This submission update form is for Research Performing Organisations, Research Funding Organisations and Publisher stakeholders of the National Open Access Monitor that have already responded to the full survey.

To view a reference PDF of this survey, please click here [\[link\]](#).

The sections of this survey are:

1. Introduction
2. Consent
3. Updating Submission
4. Change Approved By

There is no deadline for responses to this survey.

Please note: all survey data will be retained and hosted on a third party (Online Surveys) server and not on a MU server. For more information on how and why this survey data is being collected, and how it will be managed, please refer to the [Stakeholder Information Sheet and Consent Form](#).

Your submission may be paused at any time by pressing "Finish Later". Respondents who click on the "Finish Later" link are taken to a page giving the survey's closing date and a 'finish later' URL. This URL can be used to return to the survey at the page on which you clicked the 'Finish later' link. The URL can be either bookmarked in your browser, or you will be asked if you would like the URL to be emailed to you.

If you decide to take part, you are still free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason and/or to withdraw your information up until such time as the contributions are actioned upon for the development of the National Open Access Monitor. The deadline to withdraw a submission from this form is COB the Thursday after your submission (in the case of Thursday submissions, the deadline is COB that same day).

If you have any questions relating to this survey, or require assistance in filling it out, please contact Dr Catherine Ferris (National Open Access Monitor Project Manager): catherine.ferris@mu.ie

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Consent

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Formal contributors to the National Open Access Monitor Project (e.g. through stakeholder surveys like this) are required to complete and return a consent form **in advance of contributing**. This is a requirement of the Maynooth University Research Ethics Procedure.

If you have not yet completed a consent form:

1. stop here
2. complete the consent form, available at [this link](#)
3. return it to catherine.ferris@mu.ie
4. and then return to this survey.

Important: if the date/time of the survey response precedes the date/time that the consent form is received, the survey response will be **immediately deleted**.

If you have completed the consent form (an image of the first page is below as a reminder), please select yes below and continue.

Purpose of the Study. I am Dr Catherine Ferris, [JReL](#) Open Scholarship Officer (Maynooth University) and Project Manager of the National Open Access Monitor Project, funded by the National Open Research Forum.

This project will develop a monitor for open access at the national level, initially through pilot reports and a national dashboard to publish, analyse and track progress towards 100% open access. The key objectives and expected outcomes are to:

- Work to arrive at a community-agreed definition for Open Access at the national level
- Build on previous NORF work, engaging with national stakeholders (DFHERIS, NORF, NORF 2022 Open Research Fund projects, HEA, research funding organisation, research performing organisations, national research infrastructures, publishers etc.) to gather and validate user requirements for Open Access monitoring
- Work with external vendors to deliver reports and a national dashboard to help Ireland publish, analyse and track open access rates at the national level.
- Document challenges that should be addressed in long-term monitoring solutions and recommend steps to be taken, including workflows for data validation and enrichment.
- Work to improve the quality and depth of data used for the national dashboard in line with international best practice through stakeholder collaboration with institutions, funders etc. and direct input or validation where possible.
- Following NORF and Science Europe recommendations, ensure that the monitor uses data and bibliographic databases that are openly accessible, is built using open infrastructure, and is publicly accessible to view and analyse.

A copy of the Project Plan is available here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7331432>

What will the study involve and what information will be collected?

Participants will be asked to provide input and contribute as representatives of stakeholder entities, over the course of the two-year project (1 November 2022-1 November 2024), in the following areas:

- to arrive at a community-agreed definition for Open Access in this context at the national level
- to validate, and if required expand on, the user stories and functional requirements of the National Open Access Monitor identified by the NORF OA Monitoring Policy Brief Group. These functional requirements should explicitly state current OA reporting metrics for each stakeholder, required data points and potential future requirements.
- to monitor and track the costs associated with contributing to this project and to provide this data to the Project Manager, for inclusion in the final report to the funder, in a pseudonymised format (to the high-level stakeholder group) to demonstrate the cost of this work to the national research system.
- to provide metadata and persistent identifiers as required, to enable the successful delivery of the pilot dashboard
- to provide feedback on the pilot dashboard
- if necessary, to work with the Project Manager to determine the impact of vendor non-deliverables
- to work with the Project Manager to identify gaps, incomplete representation, or errors in pilot data.
- to work to improve the quality and depth of data used for the national dashboard.

1. Have you completed the National Open Access Monitor Project Stakeholder Consent Form, and returned it to catherine.ferris@mu.ie? *

Yes

No

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Consent Disclaimer

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The National Open Access Monitor Project Stakeholder Consent Form allows participants to choose to be pseudonymised, if you would rather your contribution was not publicly attributed to you and your organisation/entity.

However, due to the nature and purpose of this survey on Organisational Identity, the **identity of your organisation/entity cannot be pseudonymised**. Therefore, while your name will remain pseudonymised, it will be evident that a representative of your organisation/entity contributed to this survey.

- If you chose pseudonymisation in the consent form, and are happy to continue with this survey under these conditions, please continue.
- If you chose pseudonymisation in the consent form, and are **not** happy to continue with this survey under these conditions, please stop here and forward this survey onto another person in your organisation/entity to complete.

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Please Identify the Submission to be Updated

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2. Unique Response Number *

(copy and paste from original submission)

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Irish Research eLibrary

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Please identify the Survey Question Number +
Survey Question which you would like to update

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3. Survey Question Number *

(copy and paste from original submission)

4. Survey Question *

(copy and paste from original submission)

5. Original Submission *

(copy and paste from original submission)

6. Updated Submission *

(please enter the new text here that you would like the original submission updated to)

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Change Approved By

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7. Your name *

8. The name of the organisation/entity that you represent *

9. Your department *

10. Your job title *

11. Your email address (the Project Manager may need to follow-up with you on your responses. Your email address will not be made public.) *

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Submit

Please click submit below to complete the survey

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[Finish later](#)

[Submit](#)

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